

INFLUENCE OF CUSP COMPLIANCE AND LAYERING METHOD ON CUSP DEFLECTION IN DENTAL BULK-FILL COMPOSITE RESTORATION.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of the layering method and cusp compliance on cusp deflection in bulk-fill and conventional composite restorations, and to examine the relationships between cusp deflection and the polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of composites. Six light-cured composites were used in this study. Two of these were conventional methacrylate-based composites, a high-viscosity universal (Z250) and a flowable (Z350) composite, whereas four were bulk-fill composites. Of the bulk-fill composites, two were high-viscosity universal composites (SonicFill, Tetric N Ceram) and two were flowable composites (SDR, Filtek Bulk Fill). One hundred eighty aluminum blocks with a Mesio-Occluso-Distal (MOD) cavity [6 (W) × 8 (L) × 4 (D) mm] were prepared and classified into three groups with cusp thicknesses of 1, 2, and 3 mm. Each group was further subdivided according to the composite layering method (bulk or incremental layering). Linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) probes were used to measure cusp deflection. The polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of the six composites were also measured. As a result, all groups with bulk filling exhibited significantly higher deflection compared with groups with incremental layering. Cusp deflection decreased as cusp thickness increased. The polymerization shrinkage ranged from 2.08% (SonicFill) to 3.52% (Z350). The flexural modulus of Z250 was the highest (9.20 GPa), while it was the lowest with Filtek Bulk Fill (4.63 GPa). The highest and lowest polymerization shrinkage stresses were recorded for Z350 (5.07 MPa) and SDR (1.70 MPa), respectively. The correlation between polymerization shrinkage and cusp deflection decreased with increasing cusp thickness. On the other hand, the correlation between flexural modulus and cusp deflection increased with increasing cusp thickness. For all groups, cusp deflection correlated strongly with polymerization shrinkage stress.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their superior aesthetic properties, resin-based composites have been widely used in dentistry. However, the polymerization of composites generally produces substantial volumetric shrinkage due to the reduction in distance between monomer molecules as they form covalent bonds. Moreover, this effect produces polymerization shrinkage stress in a confined cavity [1]. Polymerization shrinkage stress may compromise the bond integrity, which in turn has been proposed to lead to a variety of clinical problems such as microleakage, marginal gap formation, recurrent caries, pulpal irritation, enamel cracking, and cusp deflection [2]. Therefore, minimizing polymerization shrinkage stress of composites is still a major challenge for dental clinicians when placing composite restorations. For example, incremental layering can minimize the configuration factor (C-factor)

thereby allowing more flow of the composite from the free surface [3-5]. A number of studies have reported considerably reduced polymerization shrinkage stress or cuspal deflection by using incremental layering compared with bulk filling [4, 6, 7].

A variety of instruments and approaches have been used to quantify linear and volumetric polymerization shrinkage of dental composites. Cuspal deflections are well described to be closely related with polymerization shrinkage [8] and cuspal compliance is an important factor that affects cuspal deflection. Thus, to obtain clinically relevant results, cuspal compliance should be similar to that observed in clinical situations. However, no study has yet investigated the effect of cuspal compliance on cuspal deflection.

Recently, many bulk-fill composites have been introduced as alternatives to conventional composites. These composites are intended to be placed and bulk-cured in one increment, up to 4 mm in height. However, little information is available regarding the polymerization kinetics of these composites. Moreover, no study has yet examined the relationship between cuspal deflection and the polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of these composites.

The aim of this study was thus to investigate the effects of the layering method and cuspal compliance on cuspal deflection in bulk-fill vs. conventional composite restorations. In addition, the relationships between cuspal deflection and the polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of various composites were also examined.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Six light cured composites were examined in this study. Two were conventional methacrylate-based composites, a high-viscosity universal (Z250) and a flowable (Z350) composite, and four were bulk-fill composites. The bulk-fill composites included two high-viscosity universal composites (SonicFill, Tetric N Ceram) and two flowable composites (SDR, Filtek Bulk Fill). Each composite was categorized as conventional or bulk-fill and high-viscosity or low-viscosity (flowable) composite according to its use and viscosity. The brand names, types, compositions, and manufacturers of the composites are listed in Table 1.

Composite	Type	Composition	Manufacturer
Z250	C, H	Bis-GMA, Bis-EMA, TEGDMA, UDMA 0.01-3.5 μm Zr/silica particles (82 wt%)	3M ESPE, St. Paul, MN, USA
SonicFill	B, H	Bis-GMA, TEGDMA, EBPDMA, SiO ₂ , glass, oxide (83.5 wt%)	Kerr, Orange, CA, USA
Tetric N Ceram	B, H	Bis-GMA, UDMA Ba-glass filler, ytterbium trifluoride, Mixed oxide prepolymer (79-81 wt%)	Ivoclar Vivadent , Schaan, Liechtenstein
Z350 flowable	C, F	Bis-GMA, Bis-EMA, TEGDMA 5-20 nm Zr/silica nano-particles, 0.6-1.4 μm nano-clusters (65 wt%)	3M ESPE
SDR	B, F	Modified UDMA, TEGDMA, EBPDMA Ba-Al-F-B-Si glass, St-Al-F-Si glass (68 wt%)	Dentsply Caulk, Milford, DE, USA
Filtek Bulk Fill	B, F	Bis-GMA, UDMA, Bis-EMA, procrilate resins Zr/silica, ytterbium trifluoride (64.5 wt%)	3M ESPE

Table 1: Brand name, type, composition, and manufacturer of each composite used in this study. Abbreviations: C, conventional composite; B, bulk-fill composite; H, high-viscosity; F, flowable

2.2 Measurement of cusp deflection

One hundred eighty aluminum blocks with an MOD cavity [6 (W) × 8 (L) × 4 (D) mm] were prepared and allocated into three groups with varying cusp thicknesses (1, 2, and 3 mm) (Fig. 1a). The inside wall of each cavity was air abraded with 50 μm Al₂O₃ powder, rinsed with water, and air dried. Then, the inside of the cavity was coated twice with a metal primer (Z-Prime Plus; Bisco, Schaumburg, IL, USA) and dried. A thin layer of Scotchbond Multipurpose Adhesive (3M ESPE) was applied and light cured for 10 s. An LED light unit (Elipar S10, 3M ESPE, St. Paul, MN, USA) was used for curing; the light intensity was 750 mW/cm². An acrylic cap with two notches on the top of the lateral wall was fabricated and placed on top of the aluminum block to prevent the composite from being pushed out of the cavity during layering.

The different cusp thickness groups were further subdivided according to composite layering method (bulk vs. incremental layering). Before mounting the specimen in the cusp deflection measurement instrument, the composite for bulk filling or the first layer of incremental filling was filled in the cavity of the aluminum block. In the bulk filling group, the composite in the aluminum block cavity was light cured from the upper surface for 20 s, the mesial side for 20 s, the distal side for 20 s, and again on the upper surface for 20 s (total, 80 s). In the incremental layering group, the composite was filled in four incremental layers, each 1 mm thick. Each layer was light cured from the upper surface for 20 s (total, 80 s). Five aluminum blocks were allocated for each subgroup (bulk or incremental) of each composite.

Cusp deflection was measured in real time throughout the curing process using two LVDT probes (AX-1, Solartron Metrology, West Sussex, UK), each with a sensitivity exceeding 0.1 μm, in a range of ± 1 mm (Fig.1b). Measurement of cusp deflection was initiated 20 s prior to light irradiation to obtain a baseline and continued up to 2000 s, at a rate of 2 data points/s (n = 5).

Figure 1(a): Dimensions (mm) of aluminum blocks with varying cusp thicknesses.
Left, 1 mm; center, 2 mm; right, 3 mm.

Figure 1(b): Instrument for measuring cusp deflection.

2.3 Measurement of polymerization shrinkage

Polymerization shrinkage was measured with the modified bonded disc method (Fig.2) [9]. Briefly, the designated amount of composite was pressed between a slide glass and a flexible cover glass (Marienfeld-Superior, Lauda-Königshofen, Germany). A metal wire spacer was used to make 0.5 mm-thick specimens. The tip of an LVDT probe was placed on the cover glass at the center of the disc-shaped composite specimen; this point was set to zero. Baseline data were obtained for 10 s, and then the curing light was turned on for 40 s ($n = 5$). The polymerization shrinkage (%) was calculated.

Figure 2: Instrument for measuring polymerization shrinkage using the modified bonded disc.

2.4 Measurement of flexural modulus

Bar-shaped specimens were generated by compressing the appropriate composite between a Teflon mold [$3\text{ (W)} \times 3\text{ (T)} \times 30\text{ (L)}\text{ mm}$] and a slide glass. The specimens were light cured and stored in dry conditions for 1 day in the dark at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Flexural modulus was measured using the three point bending method with a universal testing machine (LF Plus, Lloyd Instruments, West Sussex, UK) at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min (supporting span length = 20 mm) ($n = 5$).

2.5 Measurement of polymerization shrinkage stress

A custom-made instrument with a voice coil motor (MGV52-20-0.5, Akribis Systems, Singapore) was used to measure the polymerization shrinkage stress (Fig.3). Briefly, a slide glass was fixed to a movable stage, which was connected to the voice coil motor. Another slide glass was fixed to an immobile stage on the opposite side of the motor. As the composite between the two slide glasses contracted due to polymerization, the slide fixed to the movable voice coil motor was pulled to the opposite slide, which was fixed on the immobile stage. This deviation was then detected by the linear encoder. Immediately, a servo amplifier provided electrical current to the voice coil motor to offset the deviation. Therefore, the distance between the two slide glasses was maintained. This feedback mechanism continued, with the servo electrical current staying proportional to the polymerization shrinkage stress. Calibration analysis revealed a linear relationship between the shrinkage force and the servo current.

The end surfaces of two 1 mm-thick slide glasses were sandblasted with $50\ \mu\text{m Al}_2\text{O}_3$ particles and covered with adhesive tape. A 2 mm-wide window was created on the taped surface, thus exposing the glass surface, which was treated with silane (Porcelain Primer, Bisco), a bonding agent (Scotchbond Multipurpose Adhesive, 3M ESPE), and light cured for 10 s. The two slide glasses were aligned 3 mm apart from one another and then fixed on the movable and immobile stages of the

instrument. After the composite was placed between the slides, baseline data were obtained for 10 s and the composite was irradiated with a curing light for 40 s. Measurements were made for each composite, at a rate of 10 data points/s, for 10 min (n = 5).

Figure 3: Instrument for measuring polymerization shrinkage stress using a voice coil motor with feedback mechanism.

2.6 Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 21.0). Multiple-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's post-hoc test ($\alpha = 0.05$) were used to compare the cusp deflection groups. Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted to investigate the relationships between cusp deflection and the polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of the composites.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Cusp deflection

The cusp deflections of Z250 fillings of different cusp thicknesses and layering methods as a function of time are shown in Fig.4. The majority of the cusp deflection was observed within 500 s, after which time cusp deflection gradually increased before reaching a plateau. Cusp deflection occurred in a stepwise manner in the incremental layering group.

The mean cusp deflections (μm) at 2000 s are presented in Table 2. The cusp deflection (μm) and reduction (%) from bulk to incremental layering for each subgroup are presented in Fig.5. Cusp thickness, layering method, and composite brand all yielded statistically significant differences ($p = 0.000$) in the cusp deflection. For instance, all groups with bulk filling exhibited significant higher cusp deflection compared with groups with incremental layering ($p = 0.000$); moreover, cusp deflection was significantly different among the 1, 2, and 3 mm cusp thickness groups ($p = 0.000$). Specifically, cusp deflection decreased with increasing cusp thickness.

Figure 4: Cusp deflection (μm) of the Z250 composite with varying cusp thicknesses and layering methods as a function of time.

Figure 5: Mean cusp deflection (μm) and reduction in deflection from bulk to incremental layering (%) for each composite according to cusp thickness and layering method. The number above each bar indicates the reduction in cusp deflection from bulk to incremental layering (%).

Composite	Layering method	Cusp thickness		
		1 mm	2 mm	3 mm
		Cusp deflection (μm)		
Z250	Bulk	35.55 ^{B,a} (1.19)	19.01 ^{B,c} (0.60)	13.37 ^{B,d} (2.01)
	Incremental	28.43 ^{CD,b} (0.88)	14.17 ^{C,d} (0.73)	8.06 ^{C,e} (0.83)
SonicFill	Bulk	30.96 ^{C,a} (0.62)	19.48 ^{B,c} (1.67)	12.67 ^{B,d} (1.35)
	Incremental	26.59 ^{D,b} (1.90)	13.57 ^{C,d} (1.16)	9.38 ^{C,e} (0.71)
Tetric N Ceram	Bulk	27.19 ^{D,a} (0.66)	14.20 ^{C,c} (0.73)	8.67 ^{C,d} (0.71)
	Incremental	23.09 ^{E,b} (0.83)	7.32 ^{D,e} (0.45)	4.62 ^{D,f} (0.10)
Z350	Bulk	50.97 ^{A,a} (2.24)	27.57 ^{A,b} (1.98)	15.94 ^{A,d} (1.12)
	Incremental	48.22 ^{A,a} (1.19)	20.95 ^{B,c} (1.74)	11.82 ^{B,e} (0.30)
SDR	Bulk	28.43 ^{CD,a} (1.48)	10.77 ^{D,c} (1.07)	4.83 ^{D,e} (0.17)
	Incremental	15.14 ^{F,b} (0.64)	6.98 ^{D,d} (0.83)	3.80 ^{D,e} (0.27)
Filtek Bulk Fill	Bulk	36.26 ^{B,a} (1.95)	14.21 ^{C,c} (1.30)	9.48 ^{C,d} (0.25)
	Incremental	23.42 ^{E,b} (0.76)	8.91 ^{DE,d} (0.66)	4.78 ^{D,e} (0.79)

Table 2: Mean cusp deflection (μm) for each group at 2000 s.

3.2 Polymerization shrinkage

Representative polymerization shrinkage curves of the composites are shown in Fig.6. Most polymerization shrinkage occurred within 100 s and gradually increased after this time until reaching a plateau. The Polymerization shrinkage (%), maximum shrinkage rate (%/s), and time at peak shrinkage rate of each composite are shown in Table 3. The Z350 composite demonstrated the highest polymerization shrinkage (3.52%), followed by Filtek Bulk Fill (3.17%), SDR (2.88%), Z250 (2.18%), and Tetric N Ceram (2.11%), while SonicFill showed the lowest shrinkage (2.08%). No significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were observed between Z250, Tetric N Ceram, and SonicFill with respect to polymerization shrinkage.

3.3 Flexural modulus

The flexural modulus (GPa) of each composite is presented in Table 3. Z250 showed the highest flexural modulus (9.20 GPa), followed by SonicFill, Tetric N Ceram, Z350, SDR, and Filtek Bulk Fill (4.63 GPa).

Figure 6: Polymerization shrinkage (%) of each composite as a function of time.

Composite	Polymerization shrinkage (%)	Max. shrinkage rate (%/s)	Time at peak shrinkage rate (s)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Polymerization shrinkage stress (MPa)
Z250	2.18 (0.06) ^d	0.35 (0.02) ^d	1.56 (0.06) ^c	9.20 (0.21) ^a	2.88 (0.13) ^b
SonicFill	2.08 (0.07) ^d	0.34 (0.02) ^d	1.79 (0.41) ^{abc}	7.97 (0.44) ^b	2.73 (0.10) ^b
Tetric N Ceram	2.11 (0.02) ^d	0.44 (0.03) ^c	1.11 (0.11) ^d	6.68 (0.25) ^c	2.82 (0.13) ^b
Z350	3.52 (0.04) ^a	0.64 (0.02) ^a	2.11 (0.07) ^a	5.79 (0.11) ^d	5.07 (0.42) ^a
SDR	2.88 (0.13) ^c	0.64 (0.01) ^a	1.67 (0.08) ^{bc}	5.62 (0.20) ^d	1.70 (0.16) ^d
Filtek Bulk Fill	3.17 (0.03) ^b	0.52 (0.05) ^b	1.94 (0.08) ^{ab}	4.63 (0.18) ^e	2.28 (0.19) ^c

Table 3: Polymerization shrinkage (%), maximum shrinkage rate (%/s), time at peak shrinkage rate (s), flexural modulus (GPa), and polymerization shrinkage stress (MPa) of each composite.

3.4 Polymerization shrinkage stress

The polymerization shrinkage stress of each composite as a function of time is shown in Fig.7. The highest and lowest polymerization shrinkage stresses were recorded for Z350 (5.07 MPa) and SDR (1.70 MPa), respectively (Table 3). No significant differences were observed between Z250, Tetric N Ceram, and SonicFill ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 7: Polymerization shrinkage stress (MPa) as a function of time for each composite.

3.5 Correlation analysis

The correlation analysis results are presented in Table 4. For 1 mm-thick cusps, cusp deflection and polymerization shrinkage showed strong and moderate correlations with bulk ($r = 0.706$) and incremental layering ($r = 0.446$) groups, respectively. Meanwhile, for 3 mm-thick cusps, cusp deflection and flexural modulus were moderately correlated ($r = 0.376$) in the bulk filling group. The correlation between polymerization shrinkage and cusp deflection decreased as cusp thickness increased. On the other hand, the correlation between flexural modulus and cusp deflection increased with increasing cusp thickness. The cusp deflection of all groups correlated strongly with the polymerization shrinkage stress ($r = 0.785 - 0.969$) and the product of shrinkage and modulus ($r = 0.657 - 0.780$).

	Polymerization shrinkage stress	Cusp deflection					
		1 mm		2 mm		3 mm	
		Bulk	Incremental	Bulk	Incremental	Bulk	Incremental
Polymerization shrinkage	0.393 *	0.706 **	0.446 *	0.282	0.328	0.099	0.17
Flexural modulus	0.033	-0.186	0.048	0.227	0.234	0.376 *	0.341
Shrinkage × Modulus	0.602 **	0.661 **	0.678 **	0.71 **	0.78 **	0.657 **	0.727 **
Polymerization shrinkage stress	1	0.832 **	0.969 **	0.885 **	0.868 **	0.785 **	0.817 **

Table 4: Analysis of correlations between the cusp deflection and the polymerization shrinkage, flexural modulus, and polymerization shrinkage stress of various composites.

4 CONCLUSION

Both conventional and bulk-fill composites showed lower cusp deflection when incrementally filled. In addition, restoration by bulk filling with high-viscosity bulk-fill composites did not achieve results comparable to those obtained with incremental layering with high-viscosity universal composites. Moreover, as the cusp thickness increased, the cusp deflection decreased and the reduction in cusp deflection achieved by incremental layering was augmented. When cusp compliance was high, polymerization shrinkage was the main factor that influenced cusp deflection. In low compliance cusps, both the flexural modulus and the polymerization shrinkage determined cusp deflection.

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